

Collaborative Governance in Stunting Management in Bolaang Mongondow District

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Abstract:- The purpose of this study was to determine and analyze the collaborative governance process in stunting prevention in Bolaang Mongondow district. The method used is qualitative research, the main data source is through structured interviews. Data analysis is the process of systematically searching and compiling data obtained from interviews, field notes, other materials so that they can be easily understood and the findings can be informed to others. Sugiyono (2011) Data Reduction, Data Presentation, Conclusions and Verification.

The collaborative governance process through interface dialogue, there are coordination meetings held 2 times a year, indicators of building trust must start from all sectors must play an active role, the government's commitment to provide supplementary food assistance with milk, eggs and biscuits for five-year-old babies, lack of village government involvement In tackling stunting, a shared understanding can be seen from the nutrition program holders every quarterly monitoring and evaluation, the temporary impact has been activated by the 2022 youth integrated service post and the government conducts door to door visits to reduce stunting cases.

Keywords:- Collaborative governance, stunting.

I. INTRODUCTION

The goal of national development is to protect the entire Indonesian nation and all of Indonesia's bloodshed, promote public welfare, educate the nation's life, and participate in carrying out world order based on freedom, eternal peace and social justice and realizing the ideals of the nation as set out in paragraph II of the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution. . One of them is efforts to improve the quality of human resources starting with the main attention to the process of growth and development of children from conception to young adulthood. During this period of growth and development, fulfilling children's basic needs such as care and nutritious food provided with love can form healthy, intelligent and productive human resources (Liputan 6.com). The problem of nutrition is a public health problem that cannot be solved by using a medical approach and health services alone. The problem of nutrition is a poverty syndrome that is closely related to the problem of food security at the household level and involves aspects of knowledge and behavior that do not support a healthy lifestyle. The state of community nutrition will affect the level of health and life expectancy which is one of the main elements in determining the success of development, handling nutrition is closely related to a nation's strategy in

creating healthy, intelligent and productive human resources.

Indonesia is a developing country that has complex problems, especially in terms of nutrition. Nutrition in Indonesia or other developing countries has cases of nutrition that are different from developed countries, namely Indonesia has multiple nutritional problems, which means nutritional status indicates that on one side of the region there is undernutrition and on the other hand there is excess nutrition.

Stunting is one of the nutritional problems experienced by toddlers, where toddlers experience failure to thrive as a result of chronic malnutrition so that toddlers are too short for their age. In general, stunting is caused by a lack of nutrition for a long time and the occurrence of recurrent infections, and these two causative factors are influenced by inadequate parenting from the womb to the first 1,000 days of birth (Izwardy, 2019). The prevalence of stunting/dwarfing in Indonesia is relatively high, if the prevalence of stunting/dwarfing in Indonesia compared to Southeast Asian countries is as follows:

Graph 1: Prevalensi Stunting di Asia Tenggara 2018

Based on the diagram above, it shows that Indonesia has the second stunting prevalence rate in Southeast Asian countries with an acquisition of 36.40% (WHO, 2018). Poverty and low parental knowledge of children's health are important factors in the high prevalence of stunting in Indonesia. This is what causes many Indonesian children to experience nutritional problems since they are still in the form of fetuses until they are 24 months old. WHO has set the maximum limit for stunting, which is 20% of the total number of children under five.

North Sulawesi Province has a high prevalence of stunting in Bolaang Mongondow district, for 2021 as many as 89 cases spread across 8 sub-districts with the largest stunting cases in Lolayan District with 73 cases and North Dumoga sub-district 8 cases (Bappeda Bolmong, 2021). This is indicated by the lack of face-to-face contact or coordination, commitment to cross-sectoral collaboration processes in tackling stunting cases.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Over the last few decades, new forms of government have emerged to replace hostile and managerial ways of policy making and implementation. Collaborative governance, as it has become known, brings together public and private stakeholders collectively forums with public bodies to engage in consensus-oriented decision-making. After reviewing 137 cases of collaborative governance across various policy sectors, we identify important variables that will influence whether this model of governance will lead to successful collaboration. These factors include face-to-face dialogue, building trust, and the development of shared commitment and understanding. We find that a virtuous cycle of collaboration tends to develop when collaborative forums focus on “small wins” that deepen trust, commitment, and mutual understanding (Ansell & Gash, 2008).

Through an analysis of the existing collaboration models, a polycentric governance framework was added in the SFIC collaborative model, thus forming a polycentric collaborative governance model, and an explanation on the topic that multiple charitable organizations participate in social governance was proposed (Wang, 2014). On the basis of three dimensions, collaborative governance theory itself, the relationship between collaborative governance and other elements and specific applications of collaborative governance theory, this paper puts forward collaborative governance theory research prospects to promote the integration and further development of collaborative governance theory (Sun, 2017).

If we are to apply this practice to Korean public administration, we need to develop an empirical theory of collaborative governance that combines the characteristics of a strong state and a collaborative instrumental theory of governance that explicitly considers group dynamics in indigenous cultures (Choi, 2014).

III. COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE

Collaborative Governance is a governing arrangement in which one or more public bodies directly engage non-state stakeholders in a collective decision-making process that is formal, consensus-oriented, and deliberative and that aims to make or implement public policy or manage public programs or assets (Choi, 2014). Collaborative Governance emphasizes six important criteria: (i) forums are initiated by public bodies or institutions, (ii) forum participants include non-state actors, (iii) participants are directly involved in decision making and are not only consulted by public bodies, (iv) . forums are organized formally and meet

collectively, (v) forums aim to make decisions by consensus (even if consensus is not reached in practice), and (vi) the focus of collaboration is on public policy or public management (Imperial, 2005).

The collaboration process according to Anshal & Gash (2018) includes:

- Face-to-face dialogue is a form of communication that is important in collaboration, because of the process of forming a mutual agreement. Direct communication (face to face) as an effort to reduce stereotypes (ie the perception of actors who see the bad side of other actors) and increase respect between actors, and with direct communication, the actors involved in collaboration become more objective in interacting.
- 2. Building trust is a necessary condition for building solid collaboration. Building trust takes a long time, this is because collaboration requires intensive (continuous) communication and adjustment to current conditions from the re-emergence of past conflicts (prehistory antagonism).
- Commitment to the collaboration process (commitment to the process) is a very important component in the collaboration process, where commitment is closely related to the original motivation of the actors in collaboration. Commitment is influenced by several factors, namely related to mutual recognition, mutual appreciation of actors, trust between actors, sense of belonging to the process, and interdependence between actors. The differences in the capacities of the actors create a sense of dependence that can grow and strengthen commitment.
- Shared understanding is the understanding that is meant is the unification of thoughts and common goals, so as to minimize the occurrence of misunderstandings between actors.
- Intermediate outcomes are small wins that will increase the expectations of each actor in the collaboration so as to increase trust and commitment.

IV. PAPER OBJECTIVE

The purpose of this study was to identify and analyze the collaborative governance process in stunting prevention in Bolaang Mongondow district.

V. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative research method, which is a contextual research that uses humans as instruments and is adapted to a reasonable situation in relation to data collection which is generally qualitative in nature (Creswell, 2002). Data analysis is data reduction, data presentation, conclusion and verification (Sugiyono, 2011).

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Lolayan Village in 2021 there are 48 cases of stunting, a national program in the context of handling stunting through a policy of handling as early as possible since pregnant women aged 0 to 33 months, known as the first 1000 days of life. Which actors are involved in stunting prevention,

namely regional apparatus organizations including: social services, women's empowerment, village community empowerment, regional education offices, housing and settlement services, food security agencies, agriculture services, communication and information services. Stunting is the same as chronic nutrition or balance disorders.

Actors in tackling stunting in Bolaang Mongondow district are: Social Service, Women's Empowerment, Village Community Empowerment, Regional Education Office, Food Security Agency, Agriculture Office and Communication and Information Service. Based on interviews and observations, there are findings in the process of collaborative governance in tackling stunting in Bolaang Mongondow district, including:

- a) Face to face dialogue
interviews with stakeholders that communicating with each other is carried out at any time through the WA group, but the implementation of a coordination meeting (Rakor) which is attended by all stakeholders involved in handling stunting in the District The Bolmong district government conducts 2 (two) times a year stunting coordination meetings, followed by Bappeda, Food Security Agency, sub-district government go to the puskesmas every month there is a posyandu where there are stunting cases to provide additional food. Coordination with public health Health office in order to check whether there is an increase in weight and height of children under five. There is always communication within the Bolmong WA surveillance group including the head of the health sector, the head of the section, the head of the Puskesmas and nutrition experts. The stunting meeting at the district level is held once a year, which was previously held at the sub-district meeting, inviting the closest companies but only to the extent that companies attend not in the form of a cooperation agreement or in any other form.
- b) Trust building
Interviews and observations have made efforts to build trust, so all sectors must play a role in stunting prevention, not only in the health sector but also in others. Prior to the occurrence of stunting, early detection of routine pregnancy check-ups for pregnant women, delivery of educational information to pregnant women for the benefits of good nutrition, measuring body weight and comprehensively from head to toe circumference. In the prevention of stunting, the health office as the technical implementer is responsible since pregnant women are called 1000 days of life (2 years) which is the age of stunting. The average stunting case is influenced by the environment affected by TB, most of them consume external drugs and stunting sufferers are also caused by early marriage.

- c) Commitment to the process
Community Health Centers or Puskesmas have the responsibility to address these problems. In January 2022 there were six cases of stunting and until June 2022 there were five cases so that in the future it can be resolved. They thought it was because there was additional food assistance, milk, eggs and Toddler biscuits from the government. Information on stunting cases by name by address only reaches the Regional Apparatus Work Unit (SKPD) but does not reach the village, the village government itself knows exactly the people affected by stunting but the lack of involvement of the village government in tackling stunting cases.
- d) Shared understanding
Interviews and observations led to the implementation of stunting coordination meetings twice a year by inviting pediatricians, the Regional Development Planning Agency, the Food Security Agency, the Health Office, the Camat and the head of the Bolmong Health Center. Meanwhile, the holder of the nutrition program has a stunting meeting every quarter (monitoring and evaluation).

Every February and August in the current year, it is the main task and function of a nutritionist to input data results into the Electronic-Disability and Community-Based Nutrition Reporting (e-PPGBM) application which is a digital platform for interconnection with sub-district governments, district governments, provincial governments to the central government.

- e) Intermediate outcomes
Based on interviews and observations, it was shown that the 2022 youth integrated service post (posyandu) had been activated in every village, giving blood-added tablets for young women to prevent anemia. The temporary impact shows that the government has carried out door to door visits to people's homes. Then there was assistance from the Ministry of Health in the form of biscuits for pregnant women as additional food, assistance from the North Sulawesi provincial social service in the form of nine basic ingredients, assistance from the North Sulawesi provincial food security agency in the form of basic necessities and planting vegetables and fruit in their respective yards.

B. Discussion

Based on the research findings above, theorization is carried out in the process of collaborative governance in overcoming stunting in Bolaang Mongondow district, including:

Face-to-face dialogue is a form of communication that is important in collaboration, because there is a process of forming a mutual agreement. The findings show that there is no collaboration with the private sector in tackling stunting because communication is the most important thing in the process of forming a collective agreement (Ansell & Gash, 2008) not just in the form of an invitation. As Emerson, et.al (2012) says that collaborative governance broadly as a

process and public structure of decision-making and policy management that involves people constructively at all levels of government, and/or public, private, and civil spheres to implement common goals which cannot be achieved in any other way. This means that the private sector is one of the actors in the collaboration process able to show its existence in tackling this stunting case. Face-to-face dialogue is at the heart of the process of building trust, mutual respect, shared understanding, and commitment to the process (Lasker & Weiss 2003; Plummer & Fitzgibbon 2004; Tompkins & Adger 2004; Warner 2006).

According to Ansell & Gash (2008) that building trust (trust building) is a necessary condition for building solid collaboration. Building trust takes a long time, this is because collaboration requires intensive (continuous) communication and adjustment to current conditions from the re-emergence of past conflicts (prehistory antagonism). To build trust, the role of all government and private sectors and the community is needed. This was reinforced by Wang (2014) that as a new way of governance, collaborative governance can strengthen interactions between citizens and government, increase public participation, coordinate the distribution of interests, and promote the alleviation and resolution of social contradictions. As Weech-Maldonado & Merrill (2000) say, a lack of trust among stakeholders is a common starting point for collaborative governance.

As Ansell & Gash (2008) said that commitment to the process of collaboration (commitment to the process) is a very important component in the collaboration process, where commitment is closely related to the original motivation of the actors in collaboration. Commitment is influenced by several factors, namely related to mutual recognition, mutual appreciation of actors, trust between actors, sense of belonging to the process, and interdependence between actors. The differences in the capacities of the actors create a sense of dependence that can grow and strengthen commitment. There are findings that the village government is less involved in tackling stunting. Meanwhile, according to Emerson, et.al (2012) decision-making must involve the community constructively at the government level so that common goals can be implemented that cannot be achieved in other ways if not the involvement of the community.

Shared understanding is the understanding in question is the unification of thoughts and common goals, thereby minimizing the occurrence of misunderstandings between actors (Ansell & Gash, 2008). Based on the findings, stunting coordination meetings are held twice a year to unify thoughts and common goals. This is supported by (Morse & Stephens, 2012) where one of the stages of collaborative governance is deliberation or deliberation in order to unite thoughts and equate common goals. Collaboration often seems to depend on achieving a virtuous cycle between communication, trust, commitment, understanding, and results (Huxham 2003; Imperial 2005).

According to Ansell & Gash (2008) the temporary impact (intermediate outcomes) is that this small victory will increase the expectations of each actor in collaboration so as to increase trust and commitment. Based on the findings, the door-to-door program to people's homes is an alternative government policy to tackle the large number of stunting cases in Bolaang Mongondow district. Edelenbos (2005) identified a three-step process that includes preparation, policy development, and decision-making, with each step having several stages.

VII. CONCLUSION

The collaborative governance process through face-to-face dialogue does not yet have cooperation with the private sector in tackling stunting. It is known that communication is the most important thing in the process of forming a collective agreement, not just in the form of mere invitations. Face-to-face dialogue is at the heart of the process of building trust, mutual respect, shared understanding, and commitment to the process. Building trust is a necessary condition for building a solid collaboration. To build trust, the role of all government and private sectors and the community is needed. There is still a lack of trust among stakeholders which is the first step for collaboration. Commitment is influenced by several factors, namely related to mutual recognition, mutual appreciation of actors, trust between actors, sense of belonging to the process, and interdependence between actors. There are findings that the village government is less involved in tackling stunting. A common understanding for unification of thoughts and common goals is that a stunting coordination meeting is held twice a year to unify thoughts and common goals. Although it is still considered not optimal in tackling stunting cases.

The process of collaborative governance through the temporary impact dimension is to increase trust and commitment. The door to door program to people's homes is one of the government's alternative programs to tackle the many cases of stunting in Bolaang Mongondow district.

VIII. RECOMMENDATION

The Bolaang Mongondow district government needs to establish a cooperation agreement with the private sector together in tackling stunting cases.

It is deemed necessary to build trust among fellow agencies, the agency related to stunting issues will be under the command of the Bolmong Regency Bappeda.

It is necessary to increase the joint commitment of the actors by involving the village government in reducing the number of stunting cases.

Campaign for stunting prevention programs to gain understanding from the village government together with the community.

The door to door program for monitoring and evaluating stunting cases needs to be maintained and improved in the form of public policies.

The use of this research is academically, to create scientific studies, especially in the field of Public Administration related to collaborative governance material. Theoretically to train and develop themselves and improve understanding of thinking through scientific writing by applying theory and knowledge. Then practically it is expected to make a positive contribution through consideration and input for local governments in improving special specifications related to stunting health services.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Ansell, C. and Gash, A., 2008. Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 18(4), pp.543-571.
- [2.] Choi, T., 2014. Revisiting the Relevance of collaborative governance to Korean public administration. *Korean Journal of Policy Studies*, 29.
- [3.] Creswell, J.W., 2002. *Educational research: Planning, conducting, and evaluating quantitative* (p. 676). Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- [4.] Edelenbos, J. (2005). Institutional implications of interactive governance: Insights from Dutch practice. *Governance*, 18(1), 111-134.
- [5.] Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T. and Balogh, S., 2012. An integrative framework for collaborative governance. *Journal of public administration research and theory*, 22(1), pp.1-29.
- [6.] Huxham, C. (2003). Theorizing collaboration practice. *Public management review*, 5(3), 401-423.
- [7.] Izwardy, D., 2019. Kebijakan dan strategi penanggulangan stunting di Indonesia. *Gerakan masyarakat hidup sehat*, pp.1-64.
- [8.] Imperial, M.T., 2005. Using collaboration as a governance strategy: Lessons from six watershed management programs. *Administration & Society*, 37(3), pp.281-320.
- [9.] Kresno, S., Nurlaela, E., Wuryaningsih, E. and Ariawan, I., 1999. Aplikasi penelitian kualitatif dalam pemantauan dan evaluasi program kesehatan. *Fakultas Kesehatan Masyarakat Universitas Indonesia bekerja sama dengan Pusat Data Kesehatan Departemen Kesehatan RI. Depok*.
- [10.] Lasker, R. D., & Weiss, E. S. (2003). Broadening participation in community problem solving: a multidisciplinary model to support collaborative practice and research. *Journal of Urban Health*, 80(1), 14-47.
- [11.] Morse, R. S., & Stephens, J. B. (2012). Teaching collaborative governance: Phases, competencies, and case-based learning. *Journal of Public Affairs Education*, 18(3), 565-583.
- [12.] Plummer, R., & Fitzgibbon, J. (2004). Co-management of natural resources: a proposed framework. *Environmental management*, 33(6), 876-885.
- [13.] Sugiyono, P., 2011. Metodologi penelitian kuantitatif kualitatif dan R&D. *Alfabeta, Bandung*
- [14.] Sun, X., 2017. Research and prospect of collaborative governance theory. *Public Policy and Administration Research*, 7(7), pp.50-53.
- [15.] Tompkins, E. L., & Adger, W. N. (2004). Does adaptive management of natural resources enhance resilience to climate change?. *Ecology and society*, 9(2).
- [16.] Warner, M. (2006). *Phantasmagoria: spirit visions, metaphors, and media into the twenty-first century*. Oxford University Press, USA.
- [17.] Weech-Maldonado, R., & Merrill, S. B. (2000). Building partnerships with the community: lessons from the Camden Health Improvement Learning Collaborative. *Journal of Healthcare Management*, 45(3), 189-205.
- [18.] Wang, S., 2014. Research on the collaborative governance model in the charity organization under polycentric perspective. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 2(09), p.263.
- [19.] Sumber lain
- [20.] <https://hot.liputan6.com/read/4525621/tujuan-pembangunan-nasional-indonesia-menurut-uud-1945-kenali-sasarannya>
- [21.] <https://apps.who.int/gho/data/node.sdg.2-2-viz-1?lang=en>
- [22.] Bappeda Bolmong Sebut Data Stunting Tahun Ini 89 Kasus - MONGONDOW.CO